

Investigating the Effect of H₂SO₄ Catalyst Concentration on Percentage Yield in Fischer Esterification of Isoamyl Acetate

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Abstract

Fischer esterification between a carboxylic acid and alcohol produces an ester and water, typically catalyzed by sulfuric acid which both accelerates the reaction through protonation and shifts equilibrium toward the ester via dehydration. This investigation examined how varying sulfuric acid concentration (0.5 M, 1.0 M, 1.5 M, 2.0 M) affects the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate synthesized from isoamyl alcohol and acetic acid.

Each concentration was tested across four trials using identical conditions: 15.0 mL isoamyl alcohol, 20.0 mL acetic acid, 10.0 mL catalyst solution, refluxed at 90°C for 15 minutes. Products were separated using a separatory funnel with sodium bicarbonate neutralization, and yields were measured gravimetrically.

Results revealed a non-linear relationship between catalyst concentration and yield. Percentage yield increased from $73.5 \pm 2.6\%$ at 0.5 M to a maximum of $85.1 \pm 2.0\%$ at 1.5 M, before decreasing to $71.6 \pm 1.1\%$ at 2.0 M. The initial increase aligns with enhanced protonation of acetic acid's carbonyl group and removal of water, driving equilibrium toward ester formation. The subsequent decline at 2.0 M likely results from competing side reactions such as alcohol dehydration to ethers, supported by qualitative observations of increasing solution coloration at higher acid concentrations. These findings establish an optimal catalyst concentration near 1.5 M for maximizing isoamyl acetate yield in Fischer esterification under these conditions.

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Introduction

Fischer Esterification is an equilibrium reaction between a carboxylic acid and an alcohol to form an ester and water (Fischer and Speier, 1895), typically catalyzed by a strong acid such as sulfuric acid. Sulfuric acid acts as a catalyst by increasing the rate of reaction and shifting equilibrium toward the ester because of its dehydrating nature (Otera, 2002). For the experiment in this paper, isoamyl alcohol reacts with acetic acid to produce the ester isoamyl acetate. The compound has a distinctive sweet, banana-like odor (PubChem, n.d.a) and is commonly used in flavorings and scents to imitate banana.

Concentrated sulfuric acid acts both as a Brønsted acid catalyst, accelerating the reaction through protonation of the carbonyl group, and as a dehydrating agent that removes the water produced, shifting the equilibrium toward ester formation (Otera, 2002). I found this nuanced, dual action mechanism interesting and wanted to test whether increasing the concentration of sulfuric acid would produce a linear increase in yield, or potential side reactions and over-dehydration would lead to a non-linear outcome. Furthermore the idea that reacting various corrosive and volatile chemicals together could produce a pleasant smelling compound, highlights one of my favorite things about organic chemistry, the idea that subtle molecular changes can completely alter the physical properties of chemical compounds.

The yield of the Fischer esterification reaction is also particularly important in industrial manufacturing processes which operate on a large scale and aim to save costs on chemicals and reduce potential waste by achieving as high of a yield as possible. Thereby, this investigation aims to answer the question of how changing the sulfuric acid catalyst concentration (0.5 M, 1.0 M, 1.5 M, 2.0 M, 2.5 M) affects the percentage yield of isoamyl

acetate (measured by an analytical mass balance) formed from isoamyl alcohol and acetic acid. Percentage yield is defined as the ratio of the actual mass of product obtained to the theoretical mass expected from stoichiometric calculations, shown as a percentage.

Background Information

Isoamyl acetate is commonly used in artificial flavourings, for its flavour and odor at large, industrial scales. Percentage yield plays a critical role in industrial scale synthesis of compounds such as isoamyl acetate where maximizing yield from chemicals and reducing byproducts and waste is vital for cost-control and potential environmental impact. Learnings about the role the acid catalysts play can also be applied to many other Fischer esterification reactions, which are used across numerous industries, such as perfume, paints, plasticizers and cosmetics (Mannu, A., & Mele, 2024). This makes the objective of this experiment particularly relevant.

In this investigation, isoamyl alcohol (IUPAC: 3-methylbutyl alcohol) reacts with acetic acid (IUPAC: ethanoic acid) to produce isoamyl acetate (IUPAC: 3-methylbutyl ethanoate), an ester with a distinctive sweet, banana-like odor (PubChem, n.d.a).

The molecule is moderately polar because of the carbonyl and ester linkage. However, the long alkyl chain makes it largely non-polar overall, so it dissolves well in organic solvents but poorly in water, this makes separation from water during extraction relatively straight forward, as it floats (PubChem, n.d.a). Isoamyl acetate has a relatively low boiling point (around 142 °C; O'Neil, 2013) because, unlike its reactants, it cannot form hydrogen bonds with itself. Thus only weaker dipole–dipole and dispersion forces hold the molecules together. As a result, it would evaporate or decompose if the reaction were simply heated in

an open flask, so a reflux apparatus is used to maintain the reaction mixture at a constant temperature without losing volatile components.

The reaction is typically catalyzed by sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), which plays two key roles in the Fischer reaction: firstly, it accelerates the rate of reaction, and secondly, it shifts the equilibrium toward the ester product, increasing yield. The former occurs because sulfuric acid acts as a proton donor, donating protons (H^+) to the carbonyl oxygen of acetic acid, forming a more electrophilic, positively charged intermediate (shown in the figure below “protonation...carbonyl”). This makes it easier for the alcohol’s oxygen (from isoamyl alcohol) to attack the carbonyl carbon (Mannu, A., & Mele, 2024), which in effect reduces the activation energy of the reaction and increases the rate of ester formation.

Figure: Protonation of the carboxylic acid’s carbonyl oxygen and subsequent addition of alcohol to the protonated carbonyl. (Though H-Cl is shown, the same process occurs with H_2SO_4). (Source from: Ashenhurst, 2025)

Secondly, as sulfuric acid has a strong affinity for water—because it forms stable hydrated species like H_3O^+ and HSO_4^- (House, 2013). It is also a powerful dehydrating agent, and removes one of the products of the reaction (water). This, in turn, encourages the reaction to continue forming more ester, in accordance with Le Chatelier’s Principle, which posits that

the removal of a product drives the reaction forward, favouring ester (product) formation (Münster, 1970).

The percentage yield of an ester in Fischer esterification can depend on many distinct factors. These include the temperature, the molar ratio of the reactants, the presence and amount of catalyst, and how well the product is separated and purified (BBC Bitesize, n.d.). In this investigation, the main focus is on how changing the concentration of the sulfuric acid catalyst affects the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate. This means that all other conditions which may or may not affect yield will be kept constant, as control variables, ensuring the effect of catalyst concentration is isolated.

Hypothesis

As the concentration of sulphuric acid increases, the percentage yield of the ester, isoamyl acetate, will initially see an increase due to a faster reaction rate and shift in equilibrium towards the ester. To test this, a null and alternate hypothesis will be employed:

- Null hypothesis (H_0): Increasing the concentration of sulfuric acid has no effect on the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate.
- Alternate hypothesis (H_a): Increasing the concentration of sulfuric acid increases the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate.

Represented mathematically:

$$H_0 : \frac{\Delta\%Yield}{\Delta[H_2SO_4]} = 0$$

$$H_a : \frac{\Delta\%Yield}{\Delta[H_2SO_4]} > 0$$

This hypothesis is justified by the fact that protonation of the carbonyl by sulfuric acid increases its electrophilicity, lowering the activation energy, while the acid's removal of water shifts the equilibrium toward ester formation. Together suggesting that increasing the catalyst concentration should positively correlate with the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate.

Hypothesized Effect of Sulfuric Acid Concentration on Ester Yield

Graph: Hypothesized relationship between sulfuric acid catalyst concentration and isoamyl acetate yield. Both null and alternate hypotheses are shown (percentage yield values are illustrative and only represent hypothesized trends).

Variables

Independent Variable

Concentration of sulfuric acid (0.5 M, 1.0 M, 1.5 M, 2.0 M, 2.5 M) used in the esterification reaction. Increments of 0.5M are chosen as these should provide statistically notable changes in yield beyond potential experimental inaccuracies, and a higher increment might overlook important subtle changes between 2 concentrations. A starting concentration of 0.5 M was chosen to provide a sufficiently low value to observe the initial trend in yield, while the

maximum concentration of 2.5 M was selected to maintain safe laboratory practice, as higher concentrations increase both the corrosiveness and volatility of sulfuric acid, making containment of acidic fumes more difficult in a school lab setting (CLEAPSS, 2022). This range balances safety, experimental scope, and the precision of measurements, ensuring that the data collected is meaningful and manageable within the practical constraints of the investigation. Four repeats of the same concentration are conducted, to find an average value, with more statistical accuracy.

Dependant Variable

The percentage yield (in mass) of isoamyl acetate is the dependent variable. It is defined as the ratio of the actual mass of a product obtained to the theoretical mass expected from stoichiometric calculations, shown as a percentage. Specifics of the stoichiometric calculations and method of extraction and measurement, which are used to derive the theoretical yield, are detailed later in Methodology and Data Analysis. The mass was measured using an analytical balance with $\pm 0.005g$ of uncertainty, making the uncertainty of the percentage yield:

$$\frac{\Delta \text{recorded mass}}{\text{theoretical yield mass}} = \frac{0.005}{17.922} \approx \pm 0.0278\%$$

Control Variables

Variable	Why the value was chosen (if applicable)	How it was controlled	Why it needs to be controlled
Volume of isoamyl alcohol (15.0 ml)	Keeping the relative volumes of reactants and catalysts low, meant reducing the risk of splashing, and the severity of spills if an accident occurred.	Measured with a 25 ml burette ($\pm 0.05 \text{ ml}$) in each trial.	To ensure that the number of moles of alcohol is consistent across trials, affecting the theoretical yield calculation.
Volume of glacial acetic acid (20.0 ml)		Measured with a 25 ml burette (The excess acetic acid ensures isoamyl alcohol

		$\pm 0.05 \text{ ml}$) in each trial.	remains the limiting reagent in all trials. Amount may also change reaction equilibrium, according to Le Chatelier's principle.
Concentration of reactants (excluding sulphuric acid)	Using pure (100% concentration) reactants ensures the number of moles is accurate, reducing variability in the reaction. It also allows the reaction to proceed efficiently and produce a measurable amount of ester as added water would shift the reaction (Le Chatelier's principle).	All experiments used the same concentrations from lab grade produced chemicals.	The molar ratio of isoamyl alcohol to acetic acid affects equilibrium conversion and yield.
Reaction time (15 minutes)	Time constraints meant, choosing a relatively short time was needed to run all trials and averages of the experiment.	All reactions refluxed for exactly 15 minutes using a timer. The delay in taking out boiling flasks and disassembling equipment amounts to an estimated 10s uncertainty ($\frac{0.1667}{15} = 1.1\%$).	Longer or shorter reaction times can increase ester yield independently of the acid catalyst concentration.
Reaction temperature (90°C)	Would increase the rate of reaction, allowing more trials to be carried out. Any hotter than 90°C would have required a heating plate or burner instead of a water bath, which introduces unnecessary excess risk.	Controlled using a water bath ($\pm 0.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ uncertainty). Before each trial started, it was always ensured the water temperature was 90°C.	Reactions need sufficient thermal energy to proceed but must not vary between trials to avoid affecting the reaction rate and consequent yield.
Number of repeats (4)	Four repeats were selected to balance experimental accuracy with available time to conduct the experiment.	All concentrations were repeated under the same conditions 4 times. The yielded mass was then averaged.	Having more or less repeats for certain concentrations would change the statistical confidence of the result unfairly compared to other results.

Isoamyl acetate isolation procedure		The same extraction and separation procedure is applied to all trials.	Consistent isolation procedures ensure that measured mass reflects the actual ester produced, reducing variability due to incomplete separation or solvent retention, and allowing accurate calculation of percentage yield.
Rate of stirring and mixing (Swirled twice, quickly after all reactants have been added, before being placed in a water bath and reflux apparatus.)		Poor mixing can create localized concentration differences, affecting the reaction rate and equilibrium. More or less mixing could also affect yield.	Standardized stirring method and speed.
Glassware moisture and water residue		All glassware is dried before use. No additional water is added during the reaction.	The presence of water shifts the equilibrium backward, reducing the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate. Removing water ensures the reaction is driven toward ester formation, in accordance with Le Chatelier's Principle.
Apparatus Configuration		Used the same reflux setup in all trials. The depth of submersion of boiling flasks was always until it made contact with the base of the water bath. It was always kept vertical.	Loss of volatile product or reactants through poor condensation in reflux apparatus can alter observed yields.

Apparatus and Materials Used

Object	Purpose	Uncertainty
Measuring Tools		
Graduated cylinders (25 mL, 50 ml)	Measure distilled water and reactant quantities	$\pm 0.5\text{ml}$
Burette (50ml)	Measure reactant volumes and stock sulfuric acid volumes with precision for making dilutions.	$\pm 0.05\text{ml}$
Digital analytical balance	Measure yield and other mass quantities	$\pm 0.005\text{g}$
Glassware and Equipment		
Separatory funnel (250ml)	Remove excess water and reactants after reaction	~0.5-2ml of water often remained.
Pasteur pipette (1.5ml)	Remove water droplets in extracted isoamyl acetate	n/a
Round-bottom flask (250 ml)	Main reaction vessel	
Reflux condenser	Recycles vapours in the reaction	
Temperature controlled water bath	Heat boiling flasks and reactants to increase the rate of reaction.	
Glass funnel	Pour solution into the separatory funnel	
Volumetric flasks (100 ml)	For mixing acid dilutions	
Beakers (100 ml, 500ml)	Store the diluted acids and excess reactants when separating with a separatory funnel.	
Test Tubes	Store the produced isoamyl acetate	
Spatula	For sodium bicarbonate	

Chemicals		
100% Isoamyl alcohol (3-methyl-1-butanol)	Reactant	n/a
Glacial (pure) acetic acid (ethanoic acid)	Reactant	
Concentrated sulfuric acid (98%)	For dilutions of 0.5 M–2.5 M; catalyst	
Distilled water	For dilutions and neutralization	
Sodium bicarbonate	Prepared as a saturated aqueous solution for neutralization	
Safety Equipment		
Lab coat	Protection	n/a
Safety goggles		
Latex Gloves		
Wash bottle with distilled water	To neutralize acid in the case of a spill / cleanup	
Paper towels		
Excess sodium bicarbonate		
Fume hood	Protect from volatile acids vapourizing into the air	

Method

Preparing Concentrations of Acid

The experiment requires pre-prepared concentrations of sulfuric acid, diluted from lab-grade 98% (18.4 M) sulphuric acid with distilled water to reach the desired concentrations for the

experiment. Finding the volumes of distilled water and acid, for a desired concentration C_2 , can be found using the formula:

$$C_1 V_1 = C_2 V_2$$

Where:

- $C_1 = 18.4\text{M}$ (concentration of stock acid)
- $V_1 =$ volume of concentrated acid to use
- $C_2 =$ desired concentration
- $V_2 =$ final volume (50.0 mL used for all reactions, gives enough acid to use in all repeats, and excess in case)

Example calculation for desired 0.5M concentration:

$$18.4 \times V_1 = 0.5 \times 50$$

$$V_1 = \frac{0.5 \times 50}{18.4} \approx 1.36$$

$$\text{Volume of water} = 50 - V_1 \approx 48.64$$

Table: Preparation of sulphuric acid solutions

Desired Concentration	Volume of sulfuric acid (ml) ($\pm 0.05\text{ml}$ uncertainty)	Volume of Water (ml) ($\pm 0.5\text{ml}$ uncertainty)
0.5 M	1.36	48.6
1.0 M	2.72	47.3
1.5 M	4.08	45.9
2.0 M	5.44	44.6
2.5 M	6.79	43.2

Acid was added to water when creating the solutions to minimize any risk of splashing 18.4 M sulphuric acid, which poses high safety risk (Hurum, 2005). And a pre-prepared solution of sodium bicarbonate (baking soda) was prepared in order to neutralize the acid after the esterification reaction is complete for each trial. Neutralizing the acid before tapping it off during filtration helps avoid excess acidic fumes from going into the air, making the mixture safer to handle during separation and filtration.

Reaction and Extraction

Each test varied acid concentration (0.5 M to 2.5 M, 0.5M increments), but used the same volumes and times and ensured all control variables were respected. For each of the 4 repeats of each concentration tested, the following method was used:

1. In a round-bottom flask add the following in order:
 - 15.0 ml isoamyl alcohol
 - 20.0 ml glacial acetic acid
 - 10.0 ml of sulfuric acid solution (of whichever concentration for that trial)
2. Swirl the flask briefly two times, then place it in the water bath (90°C) and immediately start a timer for 15 minutes.
3. Immediately assemble the reflux setup using a condenser above the opening of the boiling flask. This ensured that any fumes are recaptured and condense back into the reaction vessel.
4. After the timer ends, remove the flask from the water bath and carefully transfer the mixture to a separatory funnel and add saturated sodium bicarbonate solution slowly to neutralize excess acid until the bubbling from the neutralization has subsided. Vent the funnel regularly to release pressure from the neutralization process.
5. Wait until the contents settle, then drain the excess reactants of the solution from the bottom of the separatory funnel into a 500ml beaker, until the smallest amount of water (and excess reactants) remains (if part of the isoamyl acetate is poured, restart

by putting everything back into the separatory funnel, wait for the contents to settle, and retry). Isoamyl acetate's slightly different refractive index and often yellow tinge (not an inherent color of pure isoamyl acetate, however) makes it easy to visually distinguish.

6. Pour the remaining contents of the separatory funnel into a test tube. After at least an hour (to allow residual water to further separate), use a pipette to suck out the droplets of water that have separated and sunk to the bottom of the test tube. This ensures that the most amount of water is removed from the mixture.
7. Decant the remaining isoamyl acetate on a zeroed scale with an empty and dry 100ml glass beaker and record the yield in grams.

Figure: Water bath and reflux setup during the reaction

Figure: Separatory funnel setup after the reaction

Risk Assessment

Fischer esterification involves the use of extremely concentrated acids, flammable alcohols, and organic compounds that can release irritating vapors, furthermore, steps require heating, handling corrosive substances, and separating layers of chemicals. Therefore, a thorough risk assessment is required to ensure safety.

Type of Risk	Consideration
<p style="text-align: center;">Safety</p>	<p>In the experiment, standard school laboratory safety procedures were strictly followed in accordance with CLEAPSS guidance (CLEAPSS, 2022). Personal protective equipment (PPE), including a lab coat, safety goggles, and nitrile gloves, was worn at all times to minimize chemical exposure. Work involving concentrated sulfuric acid, glacial acetic acid, and ester vapors was conducted in or near a fume hood, and the workspace remained well-ventilated during heating and separation to prevent fume accumulation. Open flames were avoided; instead, a hot water bath or heating mantle was used to minimize the fire risk posed by flammable organic vapors. Acids were carefully neutralized with a sodium bicarbonate solution before separation, which reduced fume irritation and allowed safer handling of the reaction mixture. All chemicals, solutions, and glassware were</p>

	clearly labelled and handled with caution to prevent cross-contamination and accidental misuse.
Environmental	Equally important were the environmental considerations, where it had to be ensured that all organic residues and acidic wastes were collected in properly labelled waste containers, in line with CLEAPSS waste disposal recommendations, rather than being disposed of via the sink. This prevented potential corrosion of drainage systems and limited the environmental impact of acidic or organic effluents. The controlled neutralization and ventilation measures helped to reduce the release of volatile and irritating vapors, such as sulfuric acid fumes, alcohol vapours or isoamyl acetate vapours—which were especially prevalent with the heat used in the experiment. This ensures a safe and comfortable working environment for all laboratory students and staff.
Ethical	This investigation did not involve any living organisms, human participants, or environmentally harmful procedures. Therefore, the experiment presents no significant ethical concerns, apart from those addressed under environmental considerations.

Data Analysis

Unprocessed Data

Table: Raw data from each repeat and concentrations.

Concentration of H ₂ SO ₄ catalyst (M)	Measured mass of isoamyl acetate product ($\pm 0.005g$)				Qualitative Observations
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	
0.5 \pm 0.02	13.04	12.14	13.35	14.16	Produced a clear substance
1.0 \pm 0.03	15.5	13.4	15.55	14.62	Same, clear substance
1.5 \pm 0.03	15.28	15.66	15.72	14.37	Took on a slight yellow tinge
2.0 \pm 0.04	13.36	12.97	12.31	12.66	Slightly darker yellow tinge
2.5 \pm 0.05	<i>incomplete</i>				<i>incomplete</i>

Due to the unforeseen depletion of acetic acid supplies in the school laboratory on the day of the experiment, I wasn't able to test the 2.5 M concentration experiment which was planned.

This limitation was beyond my control and affected only this specific concentration run. Implications of this omission of data on 2.5 M test are discussed in evaluation.

Data Processing

The average mass of isoamyl acetate produced across 4 repeats was calculated as follows:

$$\text{mean} = \frac{1}{4} \times (m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4)$$

For example, with the set of data from a concentration of 0.5 M:

$$\text{mean}_{0.5M} = \frac{1}{4} \times (13.04 + 12.14 + 13.35 + 14.16) = 13.1725 \approx 13.17 \text{ g}$$

To calculate the percentage yield, first calculating the theoretical stoichiometric yield of isoamyl acetate is necessary. In each trial, 15.0 ml of isoamyl alcohol and 20.0 ml of glacial acetic acid were used. Using known densities, the mass and then the number of moles of each reactant can be found.

For isoamyl alcohol (density $0.809 \text{ g} \cdot \text{ml}^{-1}$, molar mass $88.15 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$) (PubChem, n.d.b):

$$\text{mass} = 15.0 \times 0.809 = 12.135$$

$$\text{moles} = \frac{12.135}{88.15} = 0.13766... \approx 0.138 \text{ mol}$$

For acetic acid (density $1.05 \text{ g} \cdot \text{ml}^{-1}$, molar mass $60.05 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$) (PubChem, n.d.c):

$$\text{mass} = 20.0 \times 1.05 = 21.0$$

$$\text{moles} = \frac{21.0}{60.05} = 0.34971... \approx 0.350 \text{ mol}$$

The molar ratio for this reaction is 1: 1:

Since acetic acid is present in excess ($0.350 \gg 0.138$), isoamyl alcohol is the limiting reagent. The reaction between isoamyl alcohol and acetic acid is 1:1, so the maximum number of moles of isoamyl acetate formed is also $0.13766... \text{ mol}$. With a molar mass of $130.19 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$, the theoretical mass of ester for all concentrations is:

$$mass_{theoretical} = 0.13766... \times 130.19 = 17.922... \approx 17.9 \text{ g}$$

Therefore, percentage yield is calculated by:

$$Percentage \ yield = \frac{\text{mean weighed yield}}{17.922}$$

For example, with the set of data from a concentration of 0.5 M:

$$Percentage \ yield_{0.5 \text{ M}} = \frac{13.17}{17.922} = 0.73485 \approx 73.5\%$$

Uncertainties

To evaluate the reliability of the conclusions drawn from this investigation, uncertainties in measurements and calculations were quantified and propagated through all derived values. In cases where multiple sources of uncertainty contributed to a final value, linear addition of uncertainties was used. This method, which is more conservative than combination in quadrature, provides a worst-case estimate of the total uncertainty and simplifies calculations.

Firstly, we find the uncertainty of the concentration of sulfuric acid catalyst created from diluting a 18.4 M stock acid. Because the volume of distilled water and sulfuric acid had different uncertainties, each concentration's uncertainty would vary slightly.

A reminder of the uncertainties of volume measurements used in the dilution:

- $\pm 0.05 \text{ ml}$ uncertainty for sulfuric acid volume

- ± 0.5 ml uncertainty for water volume

The following process was used to calculate each concentration's uncertainty. The formula for calculating water and acid volumes is $V_{acid} = \frac{50 \times C_{desired}}{18.4}$, $V_{water} = 50 - V_{acid}$, respectively. Therefore, because measured quantities are being multiplied, we add the relative uncertainties. For example, to find the relative uncertainty for 0.5 M dilution:

$$\frac{\Delta C_{desired}}{C_{desired}} = \frac{\Delta V_{water}}{V_{water}} + \frac{\Delta V_{acid}}{V_{acid}} = \frac{0.5}{48.6} + \frac{0.05}{1.36} = \pm 4.705\%$$

To convert to an absolute uncertainty:

$$4.705\% \text{ of } 0.5 \text{ M} \approx \pm 0.02 \text{ M}$$

Next, to find the uncertainty of the percentage yield, first we find the uncertainty of the theoretical total yield. Total yield depends on the molar quantity (see data processing) of the limiting reagent: isoamyl alcohol. Because acetic acid is in considerable excess, uncertainty of that measurement has no direct impact on theoretical yield and won't be considered. Using a burette with ± 0.05 ml uncertainty to measure acetic acid:

$$\Delta mass = 0.05 \times 0.809 = 0.04045$$

$$\Delta moles = \frac{0.04045}{88.15} = 4.5888... \times 10^{-4} \approx 0.000459 \text{ mol}$$

$$\Delta mass_{theoretical} = 4.5888... \times 10^{-4} \times 130.19 = 0.059741... \approx \pm 0.06 \text{ g}$$

Next, as the measured yield in grams is averaged across 4 repeats, to find the uncertainty for each mean, calculate the standard error of mean, $SEM = \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$, where s is the standard deviation across mass measurements of the 4 repeats and n is the number of repeats (4). For example, using the 1 M concentration test, where the standard deviations of masses was 0.889:

$$SEM = \frac{0.889}{\sqrt{4}} = 0.4445 \text{ g}$$

Accounting for the ± 0.005 grams from the mass balance, the final absolute uncertainty for the mean mass would be:

$$0.4445 + 0.005 = 0.4495 \approx \pm 0.45 \text{ g}$$

Finally, as $Percentage \text{ yield} = \frac{Mass \text{ of actual yield}}{Theoretical \text{ Yield}}$, we add the relative uncertainties of the recorded mass and theoretical yield, to find the relative uncertainty of percentage yield for each trial:

$$\frac{\Delta Percentage \text{ Yield}}{Percentage \text{ Yield}} = \frac{0.06}{17.9} + \frac{SEM+0.005}{Mass \text{ of actual yield}}$$

For example, to find the absolute percentage yield uncertainty of the 1 M concentration experiment (which has a mean mass of 14.77 g and percentage yield of 82.4), using the same absolute uncertainty for the mean mass calculated previously (± 0.45 g):

$$\Delta Percentage \text{ Yield} = \left(\frac{0.06}{17.9} + \frac{0.45}{14.77} \right) \times 82.4 = 2.7867 \approx \pm 2.8$$

Table: Other miscellaneous uncertainties and possible effect / significance

Variable	Uncertainty	Effect / Significance
Time to remove	+ 10s	Systematic error; no meaningful impact on results
Temperature of Water bath	± 0.2 °C	Insignificant and likely systematic; same water bath was used across trials.
Final mass of isoamyl acetate	~1-2ml of water often remained in the extracted isoamyl acetate, causing an estimated systemic error of +1–2 g.	Moderate random error, but likely mostly systematic and constant across trials because of standardized procedure.
Time to allow water to separate from isoamyl acetate	± 30 minutes	Likely negligible to yield as qualitative observations showed that water often separated within 20m of rest.

Processed Data

Table: Concentration of sulfuric acid catalyst with average mass and percentage yield

Concentration of H ₂ SO ₄ catalyst (M)	Average mass of isoamyl acetate product (g)	Percentage yield (%)
0.5±0.02	13.17±0.42	73.5±2.6
1.0±0.03	14.77±0.45	82.4±2.8
1.5±0.03	15.26±0.32	85.1±2.0
2.0±0.04	12.83±0.23	71.6±1.1
2.5±0.05	<i>incomplete</i>	<i>incomplete</i>

Effect of Sulfuric Acid Concentration on Isoamyl Acetate Yield

Graph: Sulfuric acid concentration vs percentage yield of isoamyl acetate (uncertainty bars are ± 2.8 percentage yield, which is the worst case uncertainty; Google Sheets doesn't allow unique uncertainty intervals for each data point)

The graph shows how the percentage yield of isoamyl acetate varies with sulfuric acid concentration. From 0.5 M to 1.5 M, the yield increases steadily from $73.5 \pm 2.6\%$ to a

maximum of $85.1 \pm 2.0\%$, before falling to $71.6 \pm 1.1\%$ at 2.0 M. This non-linear pattern suggests that increasing acid concentration initially enhances the reaction, but at higher levels the effect reverses, perhaps caused by factors which are discussed in the conclusion. The average percentage yield seems reasonable at 78.15%, compared in another study when using equal amounts of isoamyl alcohol and acetic acid 65% yield was achieved (Ashenhurst, 2025).

Considering measurement uncertainty across all data points, the error bars between 0.5 M and 1.5 M do not overlap, implying that the observed increase is significant within experimental error. The slight overlap between 1.0 M and 1.5 M suggests that the yield may already be leveling off. The uncertainty at 2.0 M is comparatively small ($\pm 1.1\%$), indicating that the decline is likely genuine rather than random error. Lastly, catalyst concentration uncertainties, which are at most ± 0.04 in the data, are sufficiently small relative to the observed trends and variability in the system, and thus do not meaningfully impact the reliability or conclusions of the analysis either.

The missing 2.5 M trial prevents confirmation of whether the downward trend continues, but the data clearly indicate an optimum near 1.5 M. A curved line of best fit highlights this pattern, showing a maximum before yield decreases. The observed trend aligns more closely with the alternate hypothesis, suggesting that acid concentration has an observable effect on ester yield, which is positive initially.

Conclusion

The results show that sulfuric acid concentration does influence the yield of isoamyl acetate, rejecting the null hypothesis, with appropriate significance as even with uncertainties taken into account, there is a clear upwards and positively correlated trend visible in the graph.

The initial rise in yield from 0.5 M to 1.5 M can be explained by the acid's catalytic and dehydrating roles in the Fischer esterification mechanism. At moderate concentrations, sulfuric acid protonates the carbonyl oxygen of acetic acid, increasing the electrophilicity of the carbonyl carbon and promoting nucleophilic attack by isoamyl alcohol (Ashenhurst, 2025). Simultaneously, its strong dehydrating property removes water from the reaction mixture, driving the equilibrium toward ester formation in accordance with Le Chatelier's principle (Münster, 1970). These combined effects explain the near-linear increase observed in the lower concentrations.

The diminishing increase between 1.0 M and 1.5 M could suggest that most reactive sites were already protonated and that further addition of acid yielded little extra catalytic benefit. Beyond this point, the significant drop in yield at 2.0 M indicates that excessive acidity begins to hinder the reaction. This deviation could occur because concentrated sulfuric acid promotes competing reactions such as dehydration of isoamyl alcohol to an ether (LibreTexts, n.d.) or even isoamylene (though this is unlikely for a primary alcohol at 90°C, LibreTexts, n.d.). A second plausible explanation is that, although already considered slightly soluble in water (~0.2 g/100 mL at 20°C, PubChem, n.d.a), the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid can influence the solubility of esters like isoamyl acetate and make separation of the ester layer less efficient, especially as the methodology didn't include waiting for layers to separate or use a dehydrating agent. The observation that the solution became more yellow (and going towards orange) supports the theory of decomposition or side product formation due to excessive acid strength (Jan, 2017).

Because the uncertainty at 2.0 M is comparatively small ($\pm 1.1\%$), this decline is unlikely to be due to random error. Considering measurement uncertainty across all data points, the error bars between 0.5 M and 1.5 M do not overlap, implying that the observed increase is significant within experimental error. However, the missing 2.5 M trial prevents confirmation of whether the downward trend continues, but the results clearly indicate an optimum near 1.5 M.

These findings align with accepted theory on Fischer esterification, which shows that when acid catalyst concentrations are too high, side reactions begin to dominate (Jan, 2017). Therefore, the results provide a clear and chemically consistent answer to the research question: increasing sulfuric acid concentration improves yield up to an optimum of around 1.5 M, beyond which further increases reduce efficiency due to competing processes.

Evaluation

Limitations and Applicability

The largest limitation is likely the missing data point for the 2.5 M result, which would have given much more detail on the trends and validation of our current conclusions. Moreover, limiting the reaction time to 15 minutes may have prevented the reaction from reaching full equilibrium, resulting in lower absolute yields and making yields reflect reaction rate more than equilibrium shifting effects of the catalyst. However, the relative differences observed between varying acid concentrations still allowed the effect of the catalyst on reaction progress to be clearly assessed. Extending the reaction time could potentially increase yields overall, but the trend with increasing acid concentration is expected to remain consistent.

Additionally, without using a dehydrating agent like magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4), it is hard to distinguish between the significance of the roles of increased isoamyl acetate solubility and side reactions or reactant decomposition that caused the yield to decrease in higher concentrations. With a dehydrating agent, the effect of increased solubility could be taken out of consideration, as all isoamyl acetate would be extracted, leaving none dissolved in the solution. Even without a dehydrating agent, waiting for the solution to settle and separate for

a longer time, across all trials, would have increased the accuracy of results and isolated causation better.

This practical limitation, along with the lack of a final 2.5 M data point, limits the findings' applicability for industrial scale usages where a dehydrating agent would realistically be used to extract the isoamyl acetate. Furthermore, temperatures in industrial scale laboratories can reach beyond 90°C, the temperature used in this experiment for school safety reasons. This means the applicability of results is confined somewhat to the temperature range in this experiment, as side reactions and correlation between temperature and catalyst concentration can be even more complex, and extrapolation to different temperature ranges isn't straightforward.

Methodological Weaknesses

Weakness	Effect / Significance	Realistic Improvement
Not enough data points (including missing 2.5 M data point)	Significant limitation as it prevents confirmation of downward trend at very high acid concentrations and limits ability to precisely identify optimal concentration. Cannot definitively prove whether yield continues decreasing or plateaus.	Complete the missing trial by obtaining additional acetic acid and running four repeats at 2.5 M using identical methodology. Or having intermediate data points (e.g., 1.25 M, 1.75 M, 2.25 M) to better map the curve around the suspected optimum.
Incomplete ester-water separation in separatory funnel	Likely a moderate systematic error that increased with acid concentration. Reduces mass measurements as some product remains dissolved in water.	Use anhydrous drying agent, like MgSO ₄ , after separation. Add directly to the organic layer in a beaker, swirl, let stand 15 minutes until ester becomes clear, then filter through filter paper. This would remove residual water effectively.

<p>Short reaction time (15 minutes) - May not reach equilibrium</p>	<p>Moderate systematic error as Fischer esterification typically requires 45-60 hours to approach equilibrium (though dependent on temperature and catalyst conditions). 15-minute reactions are likely too far from equilibrium, meaning measured yields likely reflect the reaction rate more than practical yield. This makes it difficult to distinguish true catalyst effects from rate effects.</p>	<p>Extend reaction time to at least 60 minutes, or conduct a preliminary study to find optimal time (sampling at 15, 30, 45, 60 minutes to determine when yield plateaus). This ensures comparison at or near equilibrium where the catalyst's effect on yield (water removal) is fully shown.</p>
<p>Contamination from unreacted isoamyl alcohol in product layer - Both ester and alcohol are less dense than water and float</p>	<p>Potentially significant systematic error. The unreacted alcohol would float with ester and be weighed as product. With only 15-minute reaction time and incomplete conversion, substantial alcohol may remain. Could overestimate yield moderately depending. This error may mask true yield differences between concentrations.</p>	<p>Use distillation to separate ester from unreacted alcohol (10°C b.p. difference allows separation) or Extend reaction time to 45-60 minutes to ensure more complete conversion.</p>
<p>Uncontrolled cooling time after removing from water bath</p>	<p>Poses a moderate random error. Reaction may continue during the cooling period and during the time it takes to neutralize the acid, with different cooling times (~1-5 minutes variation) leading to different actual reaction times. However, because the neutralization step used a large volume of cooler, basic solution, the reaction likely slowed down rapidly, making extra minutes unlikely to cause significant extra reaction.</p>	<p>Immediately quench the reaction by plunging the round-bottom flask into an ice bath for a standardized time (e.g., 2 minutes) after removing it from the water bath. This rapidly drops temperature below reaction threshold and halts reaction. Record temperature with thermometer to confirm it is less than a standardized temperature (e.g., <30°C) before transfer.</p>

<p>Variable separation waiting time - Inconsistent rest period for water-ester separation in test tube</p>	<p>Moderate random error. Incomplete phase separation means water remains in the ester layer, artificially inflating mass measurements by ~1-2g. Shorter waiting times would retain more water, systematically overestimating yield.</p>	<p>Standardize resting time or use a dehydrating agent such as anhydrous magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4) to remove all excess water, then filter.</p>
<p>Product loss due to adherence to glassware (separatory funnel, round-bottom flask, test tube walls)</p>	<p>Moderate systematic error. The viscous ester coats glassware surfaces. This weakness is prevalent as contents of the reaction were transferred between many pieces of glassware (e.g. boiling flask, separatory funnel, test tube, beaker). Error could also be random if technique was inconsistent.</p>	<p>Rinse all glassware with small portions (2-3 mL) of dichloromethane (DCM) or diethyl ether to dissolve remaining ester, combine rinses with main product, then evaporate the volatile solvent using a warm water bath or rotary evaporator. Weigh only after complete solvent removal. This will recover nearly all the product.</p>

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